

مركز قيادة
قوات السلطان المسلحة

From: Major D.H. Inshall,
HEAD QUARTERS
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Dear Andrew,

Further to my last letter I can give you the latest situation which I am afraid is not too promising.

It appears that the appointment as curator of the projected museum has now been confirmed to be the person I mentioned and he will commence it in December. We must naturally make the most of the situation as it now stands and I must ask you to forget the matter concerning this that I mentioned in my last letter, particularly if you hope to be possible you came here at a later date. I can not in all honesty avoid giving you the full background as David Stranach had already mentioned the appointment to you.

What we can hope is that this will start the government machinery going in the right direction and possibly create other vacancies as a result. There will naturally remain the need for a full-time archaeologist here, for our curator designate is only knowledgeable in the late Islamic and modern field of Omani History.

I believe I mentioned in my letter that Dr Karen Frisfeld had been invited to bring an expedition here later this year, as a result of her short survey in the Spring. David Stranach took a photograph of her initial report while I was in Telman and I gave my copy to the British Museum.

Yesterday I spoke to the Director General of Education who said that he had had a number of requests

to allow expeditions to come from organisations who were prepared to finance themselves. They included "an American team, a British University team, and a team of British Archaeologists who are coming to Bahain and who would like to come here as well". He could not give me the names at that time. He has decided that he will not make any decisions regarding their visit until Dr Karen Frifeld has arrived and he has been able to discuss it fully with her. This is naturally to avoid any awkward overlapping.

It appears to me that whilst these people, assuming they are fully qualified, competent and responsible, are prepared to come without financial help from the Omani government there is little prospect of the government inviting other people to come at govt expense. (None the less, Dr Karen Frifeld's expedition is being financed by Oman, the decision based on her work elsewhere on this side of the Gulf.) All this underlines our need for a permanent qualified adviser to ensure the right people come. It would appear that Karen Frifeld will fill this role in the short term, but she is only scheduled to be here for about 3 months.

I will strongly advise that you are invited to come (at govt expense of course) but mine is a small voice in this rather disorganised world! She arrives in late November. I wonder whether you know her and whether you would be able to persuade her to advise the govt to invite you? This would seem to be the best bet assuming you know her well enough or that she knows about your work.

I cannot express how disappointed I am that the museum possibility has fallen through, because in every field this country needs young (rather than old) people with unlimited enthusiasm to lead the Omanis. Also the climate is fairly demanding physically. There are so many opportunities here. I do hope there will be a chance for you to visit us here not too long hence,

so you can see it all for yourself.

I would be very glad to hear from you any comments ~~or~~ queries or suggestions on the points I've mentioned so far in these two letters.

I'm not one who finances the British Institute in Tel Aviv, but I wonder whether they would consider sponsoring you to ~~do~~ set up the same organisation here. Having seen David Stranach's achievements there I immediately saw the value of having a similar set-up here. I could scarcely think of a better use for the 250 year old castle which we use as our Face HQ here and which we are due to vacate in about two years' time.

With kind regards,

Yours sincerely,

David Inall